

Research Article

Survey on Awareness and Health Impact on Prolong Use of Electronic Wearable Devices Among Students

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Electronic wearable devices have become increasingly popular among students for health monitoring, communication, and lifestyle management. With the rising use of devices such as smartwatches, fitness trackers, and earbuds, concerns regarding their prolonged use and potential health impacts have also emerged. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 150 students using a self-structured questionnaire to assess awareness, usage patterns, and associated physical and psychological effects. The findings showed that most students were familiar with and actively used wearable devices for music, fitness tracking, and notifications. While these devices improved health awareness, some users reported discomfort, ear-related issues, anxiety, and dependence on device data. Limited awareness regarding safe usage was also observed. Overall, wearable devices provide benefits but may cause adverse effects if used excessively. Proper awareness and guidance are essential for safe and responsible use among students.

Keywords: Wearable devices, Awareness, Health impact, Students, Smartwatch, Earbuds, Prolonged use, Digital health.

INTRODUCTION

Wearable electronic devices have become a common part of daily life, combining healthcare and digital technology. Devices such as smartwatches, fitness trackers, smartrings, and health-monitoring patches are worn on the body to track activities and health parameters like heart rate, steps, sleep, and oxygen levels. They also provide notifications and support users in managing their daily routines. With advancements in sensors, wireless connectivity, and mobile technology, these devices allow continuous health monitoring outside clinical settings and help individuals become more aware of their health. However, prolonged use of wearable devices raises concerns regarding their effects on users. While they can promote physical activity, support disease management, and encourage preventive care, they may also lead to issues such as skin irritation, mental stress, dependency on data, and reduced long-term engagement. Therefore, it is important to understand both awareness and health impacts associated with the

use of wearable devices to ensure their safe and effective use.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES:

AIM:

To assess the awareness, usage patterns, and health impacts associated with the prolonged use of electronic wearable devices among students.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To evaluate the level of awareness of students regarding wearable devices (smartwatches, fitness bands, wireless earbuds, etc.)
2. To study the frequency, duration, and purpose of wearable device use among students.
3. To assess the perceived benefits (fitness, convenience, connectivity) and negative impacts (eye strain, sleep disturbance, anxiety, hearing problems, etc.) reported by students.

4. To analyze differences in usage patterns among students.

METHODOLOGY:

Study design: A self-made questionnaire was distributed to 150 student from different streams, who agreed to participate in the study. The outcomes of this study were to evaluate the awareness and health impact of prolonged use of electronic wearable devices.

Study procedure: Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire to obtain information about the awareness and role of students in addressing security and issues related to prolonged use of electronic wearable devices. Face- to-face inter views were conducted with students to minimize the risk of any and to avoid incomplete survey.

Location of study: The survey covered in college and school at Wardha district.

Study population: The study involved 150 Students (undergraduate or postgraduate) enrolled in colleges/schools.

Data collection method: Paper-based questionnaires were formed. The survey focused on assessing the students for awareness and health impact of prolonged use of electronic wearable devices.

Score calculation: Each student's responses were scored based on their level of awareness and knowledge about the prolonged use of electronic wearable devices

4. Questionnaire:

1. Are you aware of electronic wearable devices (e.g., smartwatches, fitness bands)?
2. Where did you first learn about wearable devices?
3. Which of the following wearable devices are you familiar with?
4. Do you currently use any wearable device?
5. What are the primary reasons you use a wearable device?

6. What brand of wearable device do you use?

7. How often do you use your earbuds?

8. Do you trust the health data from your wearable device?

9. On average, how many hours per day do you wear the device?

10. Do you wear your device while sleeping?

11. Are you aware that wearable devices emit low-level radiation (e.g., Bluetooth, Wi- Fi)?

12. If your wearable gives incorrect health information (false high heart rate, etc.), how would you respond?

13. How safe are wear able devices for long-term daily use?

14. Do you feel discomfort wearing the device for long hours?

15. Do you trust the health data from your wearable device?

16. Have you experienced any mental/emotional effects?

17. Do you think wearable devices are accurate in tracking health metrics?

18. Do you feel mentally stressed if your wearable battery dies?

19. Have you ever consulted a healthcare professional about using a wearable device or earbuds?

20. Have you experienced any physical discomfort or health issues related to wearable device usage (e.g., ear discomfort from earbuds)?

21. Have you ever changed your physical activity or diet solely based on your wearable data?

22. Have you experienced any changes in sleep quality or duration since using a wearable device?

23. Have you noticed any changes in stress or anxiety levels since using a wearable device or earbuds?

- 24. Does your wearable device make you more conscious of your health/fitness?
- 25. Do you think wearable tech is leading to over-dependence on data for self-health judgement?
- 26. Do you use earbuds to avoid social interactions in public space?
- 27. Which of these physical issues have you faced due to wearing earbuds for long hours?

- 28. Have you made any lifestyle changes based on insights from your wearable devices?
- 29. Has your social behavior changed due to using wearable devices?

RESULT AND RESPONSE:

- 1. Are you aware of electronic wearable devices (e.g. smartwatches, fitness bands)?

- 2. Where did you first learn about wearable devices?

- 3. Which of the following wearable devices are you familiar with?

- 4. Do you currently use any wearable device?

5. What are the primary reasons you use a wearable device?

6. What brand of wearable devices do you use?

7. How often do you use your earbuds?

8. Do you trust the health data from your wearable devices?

9. On average, how many hours per day do you wear the device?

10. Do you wear your device while sleeping?

11. Are you aware that wearable devices emit low-level radiation (e.g., Bluetooth, Wi-Fi)?

12. If your wearable gives incorrect health information (false high heart rate, etc.), how would you respond?

13. How safe are wear able devices for long-term daily use?

14. Do you feel discomfort wearing the device for long hours?

15. Do you trust the health data from your wearable device?

16. Have you experienced any mental/emotional effects?

17. Do you think wearable devices are accurate in tracking health metrics?

18. Do you feel mentally stressed if your wearable battery dies?

19. Have you ever consulted a healthcare professional about using a wearable device or earbuds?

20. Have you experienced any physical discomfort or health issues related to wearable device usage (e.g. ear discomfort from earbuds)?

21. Have you ever changed your physical activity or diet solely based on wearable data?

22. Have you experienced any changes in sleep quality or duration since using a wearable device?

23. Have you noticed any changes in stress or anxiety levels since using a wearable device or earbuds?

24. Does your wearable device make you more conscious of your health/fitness?

25. Do you think wearable tech is leading to over-dependence on data for self-health judgement?

26. Do you use earbuds to avoid social interactions in public space?

27. Which of these physical issues have you faced due to wearing earbuds for long hours?

28. Have you made any lifestyle changes based on insights from your wearable devices?

29. Has your social behavior changed due to using wearable devices?

DISCUSSION

The survey was conducted among 150 students to assess their awareness, usage, and health impact of wearable electronic devices and earbuds. The finding shows that the 98.6% students used wearable devices, while 1.4% does not use. The survey highlights 76.5% are familiar with smartwatch, 58.4% are familiar with earbuds, 21.5% are familiar with fitness tracker, 14.1% are familiar with medical wearable and 13.4% are familiar with other wearable devices. During survey we found that, about 54.4% of students knew about devices from friends/family, 32.2% from social media, 10.7% from TV/news. 2.7% from internet search and 0% from healthcare providers. This highlights that informal sources of information play a bigger role than formal health education in spreading awareness about wearable technologies. The survey highlights that, 52.4% students not experienced mental/emotional effect, 19% students experienced stress about goals 17% students experienced feeling dependent and 11.6% students experienced anxiety from monitoring. During this survey 57.8% students does not experienced any physical discomfort or health issues and 42.2% students have experienced it. The survey found that 40.4% students does not change their physical activity or diet solely based on wearable data, 30.8% students

occasionally, 15.8% students not used it for health decisions and 13% students faced regularly. In this survey 4% students does not face any physical issues to wearing earbuds for long time, 20.4% students faced inner ear itching or swelling, 18.4% students faced other issues, 13.6% students faced skin irritation around the ear and 10.2% students faced soreness from silicon tips. From this data 59.2% students not changed in stress anxiety levels since using a wearable device or earbuds, 23.8% students reduced stress or anxiety levels since using a wearable device or earbuds and 17% students increased stress or anxiety levels since using a wearable device or earbuds. About this data, 34% students sometimes used earbuds to avoid social interactions in public space, 25.9% students rarely used earbuds to avoid social interactions in public space, 23.8% students regularly used earbuds to avoid social interactions in public space and 16.3% students never used earbuds to avoid social interactions in public space. This data indicates 77.9% students does not consulted a healthcare professional and 22.1% students had consulted about using a wearable device or earbuds. Overall, the discussion suggest that wearable devices have both positive as well as negative impact. They improve convenience and health awareness but may lead to over-dependence, mental pressure, and reduced social interaction if not used carefully.

CONCLUSION

The finding of survey shows that wearable electronic devices are quiet popular and mostly used among students. Most of the students uses the devices for music listening, health monitoring or tracking and support their lifestyle. Rather than healthcare professional, most of the students learn about these devices from family, friends and social media. While wearable technology have helped students to become more aware about their personal health, its overall impact depends on how responsibly they are used. Few of the students experience anxiety, stress, or feel dependent because of constant health tracking, and least of them have consulted to healthcare professional about using of devices. This highlights that there is a need for proper education and guidance to help students for better understanding the health data accurately and use wearables responsibly. Professional guidance and awareness campaigns can help maximize wearable technology's positive effects while reducing its negative emotional and social effects. With accurate knowledge and balanced usage, wearable devices can be powerful tools for promoting fitness, improving health, and supporting more mindful lifestyles.

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Cite: Ashita Ramteke*, Rutuja Khond, Kashif Sheikh, Pratiksha Hanmante, Nitin Indurwade, Survey on Awareness and Health Impact on Prolong Use of Electronic Wearable Devices Among Students, *Int. J. Med. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (5), 390-401. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20092804>